

MAS-ML TOOL INSTALATION TUTORIAL

PREPARATION

Required:

1. Windows 10
2. Eclipse Modelling Tools

<http://www.eclipse.org/downloads/packages/eclipse-modeling-tools/oxygen1>

Figure 1 - Eclipse Modelling Tools

Attention: Eclipse Modeling Tools must be downloaded, NOT Eclipse IDE or other versions. We are going to MODEL and not CODE, so the Eclipse Modeling Tools must be used/downloaded, so if the Eclipse IDE for Java EE Developers is used, or anything other than the first (Eclipse Modeling Tools), the MAS-ML plugins They will NOT work.

3. Download MAS-ML 2.0 Plugins at <https://github.com/rendleyarnou/tcc-ii-psmarcs/tree/main/Documentos/5.%20Projetar%20sistema%20multiagente%20com%20MAS-ML%202.0/plugins>

INSTALATION

1. Unzip Eclipse
2. Unzip MAS-ML tool Plugins
3. Copy the unzipped MAS-ML tool folder the eclipse folder **dropins/plugins**

Figure 2 - MAS-ML 2.0 plugins copy

TESTING

1. Open Eclipse
2. Select New>Java Project – insert the project name (in this example it is teste) and select finish

Figure 3 – Creation of a new project

3. Click with the right button on the src folder and select New>Example>Masml Diagram>Finish

Figure 4 – Finishing the creation of a new MAS-ML diagram

Fonte: Elaborada pelo autor.

4. The next step is insert a class

Figure 5 – Adding a new class on eclipse

